

POLYCYCLIC SYSTEMS. PART VII. STUDIES IN THE FORMATION OF ARYL-CYCLOHEXENONE DERIVATIVES BY THE ROBINSON-MANNICH BASE SYNTHESIS

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The Michael-type reaction using the methiodide of aryl β -dimethylaminoalkyl ketones and a few β -oxoesters, e.g., dimethyl β -oxoadipate, its α -methyl derivative and β -oxopimelate have been studied in details. Several *p*-anisyl-cyclohexenones (e.g., VII & VIII) have been synthesised with a view to their possible synthetic uses in the steroidal sex-hormones. The reaction of 4-diethylaminobutan-2-one methiodide with methyl α -methyl- β -oxoadipate (Robinson and Seijo, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 582) has been reinvestigated.

All these reactions afford interesting observation regarding the *trans*-esterification of the intermediate aldolate ion

In Parts II and VI of this series (Nasipuri *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2734; 1960, 1571) a method has been described for the synthesis of hydrochrysene and hydrophenanthrene derivatives by the application of the Robinson-Mannich base synthesis (du Feu, McQuillin and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1937, 53) to aryl methyl ketones. The reaction which consists in the Michael-type condensation of the methiodide of β -dimethylaminoethyl aryl ketones with methyl β -oxoadipate, affords in a single step and in excellent yield, 2-aryl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enyl acetate or derivatives (e.g., VIII). In the present communication, we wish to record the results of some further extensions of this reaction leading to the synthesis of compounds (VII: R=H, Me) with the ring-carbomethoxyl group in *tact*, thus permitting further elaboration of the system to that of steroidal hormones by more or less standard methods (cf. Johnson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 1995).

4-Methoxyacetophenone, prepared according to the new method of Dominguez *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1954, 76, 5150) was converted into β -dimethylamino-*p*-methoxypropiofenone (I) by the usual Mannich reaction. The methiodide was then condensed with dimethyl β -oxoadipate (II: R=H; $n=2$) in presence of methanolic potassium methoxide. The product afforded an acidic fraction, m.p. 168°, identified as 2-*p*-anisyl-5-carbomethoxy-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylacetic acid (VII: R=H) (Turner, *ibid.*, 1951, 73, 1284; Johnson *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) in about 60% yield. A similar reaction of the methiodide with methyl α -methyl- β -oxoadipate (II: R=Me; $n=2$) furnished the acid-ester (VII: R=Me), m.p. 130° (Johnson *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) in 42% yield. The latter reaction furnished, in addition, a neutral fraction from which methyl 2-*p*-anisyl-5-methyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylacetate (VIII: R=Me), m.p. 68°, was isolated in 35-37% yield.

The acid-esters (VII: R=H, Me) were hydrolysed and re-esterified to respective methyl cyclohexenone-acetates (VIII: R=H, Me), the former being previously prepared by Turner (*loc. cit.*) in a different route.

The formation of these acid-esters in the reaction is rather interesting, but not quite unexpected. The initial product of the Michael addition is the dioxo-ester (III) which then forms an aldol. The resultant anion of the aldol (IV) can undergo intramolecular *trans*-esterification in two ways: either (a) with the acetic acid side-chain forming the γ -lactone (V), or (b) with the ring-carbomethoxyl group giving rise to the bridged δ -lactone (VI). Between these two, the first alternative is obviously preferred and the product (V) on base-catalysed ring-opening furnishes

the acid-ester (VII). The 1:4-lactone structure (VI), on the other hand, will undergo base-catalysed ring-opening with simultaneous decarboxylation, giving rise to the neutral ester (VIII).

Examples of such extensive decarboxylation in aldolate ion having a carbalkoxy group appropriately situated for *trans*-esterification are already in record (Novello *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, **75**, 1330; Logan *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1954, **76**, 4127; Horning *et al.*, "Org. Syntheses", 1947, Vol. 27, p. 27). The presence of the acetate side-chain in the present case, thus, has a protecting influence on the ring-carbomethoxyl group, providing an alternative and easier way of *trans*-esterification.

It is interesting to observe that in the condensation with methyl α -methyl- β -oxoadipate, a substantial amount (about 35%) of aldol undergoes 1:4-*trans*-esterification, as evident from the isolation of the neutral decarbomethoxylated ester (VIII: R=Me) directly from the reaction mixture. Reaction with unsubstituted methyl β -oxoadipate, on the other hand, afforded no such decarboxylated product. The reason for this differential behaviour is, however, not quite apparent.

In order to study this point further, ethyl β -oxopimelate (as II: R=H; $n=3$), prepared by the ammonolysis of ethyl 2:4-dioxoheptane-1:5-dicarboxylate (Bardhan and Nasipuri, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 350) was used instead of methyl β -oxoadipate, in the condensation with the methiodide of β -dimethylaminopropiophenone (Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd ed., p. 911). No acidic fraction, however, could be isolated from the reaction mixture, the sole product being ethyl

β -2-phenyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylpropionate (IX), isolated in 50% yield. Obviously, the intermediate aldolate ion undergoes 1:4-*trans*-esterification exclusively, in preference to the alternative δ -lactone formation with the propionate side-chain, the 5-carbomethoxyl group being subsequently eliminated in the base-catalysed ring-opening process.

The substituted propionic acids, obtainable by the above sequence of reactions, provide important starting materials for the synthesis of polycyclic systems with seven-membered ring, a preliminary account of which has already been reported from our laboratory (Guha and Nasipuri, *Science & Culture*, 1960, 25, 492).

It may be relevant to mention in this connection, the reaction of the methiodide of 4-diethylaminobutan-2-one with methyl α -methyl- β -oxoadipate, carried out by Robinson and Seijo (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 582) who failed to obtain the desired condensation product (methyl ester of XVI) in any reasonable yield. In the light of the present discussion, it is apparent that the initial Michael addition product (X), on aldol condensation, can give rise to two aldolate ions (XI & XII) which in turn can undergo intramolecular *trans*-esterification in three ways to yield the lactones (XIII, XIV & XV). The first two, on base-catalysed ring-opening, will furnish acidic products (XVI & XVII) and the third (XV) will undergo decarboxylation to furnish a neutral ester

(X)

(XI)

(XII)

(XIII)

(XIV)

(XV)

(XVI)

(XVII)

(XVIII)

(XVIII). On reinvestigation of this reaction under modified experimental condition, acidic materials were indeed obtained in good yield (70%). The acid could not be induced to crystallise. It was esterified with diazomethane and the ester afforded elemental analysis corresponding to the methyl ester of the acid (XVI or XVII). Further investigations on the structure of the product are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

β-Dimethylamino-*p*-methoxypropiofenone (I).— 4-Methoxyacetophenone required for this purpose was prepared by acetylating anisole with iodine as catalyst according to the method of Dominguez *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). A mixture of 4-methoxyacetophenone (25 g.), dimethylamine hydrochloride (16 g.), paraformaldehyde (6 g.), ethanol (30 c.c.) and HCl (conc., 0.5 c.c.) was refluxed on the water-bath for 4 hrs. After removal of most of the alcohol under reduced pressure, the crystalline hydrochloride was dissolved in minimum quantity of water, extracted with ether to remove any unchanged ketone, and the cooled aqueous solution was basified with 40% KOH solution. The aminoketone was extracted thoroughly with ether, dried (K_2CO_3) and the residue (30 g.), m.p. 32-33°, after evaporation of the solvent was directly used for the preparation of the methiodide.

2-*p*-Anisyl-5-carbomethoxy-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylacetic Acid (VII: R=H)—The above aminoketone (10.5 g.) was dissolved in dry thiophene-free benzene (50 c.c.), cooled in an ice-bath and methyl iodide (3.6 c.c.) was slowly added with stirring. Stirring was continued for 4 hrs. more at room temperature. To the crystalline methiodide, thus obtained, was added a methanolic solution of potassium derivative of methyl β -oxoadipate, prepared from potassium (2 g.), anhydrous methanol (25 c.c.) and β -oxo-ester (11.3 g.). The whole mass was then stirred at the room temperature until the crystalline methiodide was gradually replaced by granular potassium iodide (2-3 hrs.). A further amount of potassium methoxide, prepared from potassium (1 g.) and methanol (12.5 c.c.), was then added and the mixture refluxed on the water-bath for 4 hrs. It was cooled, decomposed with 2*N*- H_2SO_4 and the organic matter taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was extracted with a saturated solution of $NaHCO_3$ till no further acidic material was left in the ethereal layer. The bicarbonate extract was cooled and carefully acidified with HCl (conc.) to provide an oily substance which quickly solidified on scratching. The solid was collected by filtration and dried to furnish the acid-ester (VII: R=H) (9.5 g.), m.p. 150-55°. On several crystallisations from ethyl acetate, it was finally obtained in light yellow prisms, m.p. 168°, λ_{max}^{EtOH} 224 and 300 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.08 and 4.10 respectively). (Found: C, 64.0; H, 5.7; equiv., 317. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{18}O_6$: C, 64.1; H, 5.6%; equiv., 318).

The ethereal layer, left after the bicarbonate extract, was washed with water, dried ($MgSO_4$), evaporated and the residue was distilled in high *vacuo* to yield two fractions: Fraction (A), b.p. 120-30°/0.3 mm (1 g.), developed a violet colour with $EtOH-FeCl_3$ solution. It is most probably methyl β -oxoadipate. Fraction (B) (0.8 g.), b.p. 210-30°/0.3mm, was not investigated further.

Methyl 2-*p*-Anisyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylacetate (VIII: R=H).— The preceding half-ester (5 g.) was hydrolysed by boiling in 10% ethanolic KOH solution for 3 hours and the crude acid (3 g.) was crystallised from ethyl acetate and petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in colorless prisms, m.p. 137°. (Found: C, 69.3; H, 6.3. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{16}O_4$: C, 69.2; H, 6.1%). Turner (*loc. cit.*) reports m.p. 137-138.5°.

It readily furnished a *dinitrophenylhydrazone* which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in red needles, m.p. 250-52° (decomp.). (Found: N, 12.9. $C_{21}H_{20}O_7N_4$ requires N, 12.7%).

The methyl ester (VIII: R = H), prepared by boiling in methanolic hydrochloric acid, was obtained as a viscous gum which crystallised from methanol in colorless plates, m.p. 95-96°. (Found: C, 70.2; H, 6.5. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$: C, 70.1; H, 6.6%). Turner reports m.p. 91° for the methyl ester (*loc. cit.*).

The ester afforded a *dinitrophenylhydrazone*, m.p. 148° (from benzene-methanol). (Found: N, 12.1. $C_{22}H_{22}O_7N_4$ requires N, 12.3%).

2-p-Anisyl-5-carbomethoxy-5-methyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylacetic Acid (VII: R = Me).—To a cooled suspension of the methiodide of the aminoketone (I) (12.0 g.) in benzene (60 c.c.), prepared as before, was added a solution of potassium (3.9 g.), and methyl α -methyl- β -oxoadipate (12.5 g.) in methanol (50 c.c.). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 hours and then refluxed on the water-bath for an additional period of 4 hours. The product was worked up in the usual way and separated into two fractions as before:

(A). The acidic fraction was isolated by $NaHCO_3$ -extraction of the ethereal solution and it afforded the acid-ester (VII: R = Me) (8 g., 41.5%) as viscous oil which solidified on keeping. This was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether and then from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (40-60°) in colorless plates, m.p. 129°. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 6.1; equiv., 331. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{20}O_6$: C, 65.1; H, 6.0%; equiv., 332). Johnson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) report m.p. 129.5-130.5°.

(B). The ethereal solution left after $NaHCO_3$ -extraction was evaporated and the residue distilled in high *vacuo* to yield (i) a low-boiling fraction (1.5 g.), b.p. 105-10°/1 mm, and (ii) a high-boiling fraction (6 g.), b.p. 195-210°/1 mm. The latter fraction solidified in the receiver. It was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°) in colorless plates, m.p. 67°. It was found to be identical with methyl *2-p-anisyl-5-methyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylacetate* (VIII: R = Me) (*vide infra*) by mixed m.p. determination and analysis. (Found: C, 70.6; H, 6.9. $C_{17}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 70.8; H, 6.9%).

2-p-Anisyl-5-methyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylacetic Acid.—The acid-ester (VII: R = Me) (6 g.) was hydrolysed by boiling 10% ethanolic KOH solution for 3 hours. The crude acid (3.7 g.) was converted directly into the *methyl ester* (VIII: R=Me), m.p. 67° (methanol), by boiling with 5% MeOH-HCl solution. A part of the crystalline ester was hydrolysed with 5% EtOH-KOH solution and the acid on several crystallisations from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (60-80°) was obtained in glistening prisms, m.p. 142-43°. (Found: C, 70.2; H, 6.7%; equiv., 275. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 70.1; H, 6.6%; equiv., 274).

Ethyl β -Oxopimelate (II: R = H; n = 3).—A stream of dry ammonia gas was passed through a solution of ethyl 4:6-dioxoheptane-1:5-dicarboxylate (30 g.) in dry ether (50 c.c.) for 45 mins., while the solution was kept cooled in a freezing mixture. After the mixture was left overnight, it was decomposed by shaking vigorously with HCl (cold, dilute) and ethyl β -oxopimelate was taken up in ether, dried, and the solvent evaporated. The residue was distilled to yield the β -oxo-ester (14.2 g., 55%), b.p. 120-21°/0.2 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4400. Hunter and Hogg (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1924) report b.p. 120-21°/0.15 mm. A good middle fraction was analysed. (Found: C, 57.4; H, 8.1. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{18}O_5$: C, 57.4; H, 7.8%).

It afforded a *phenylpyrazolone* derivative on being heated with phenylhydrazine. It was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in plates, m.p. 245° (decomp.). (Found: C, 65.4; H, 6.7; N, 10.4. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{18}O_3N_2$: C, 65.7; H, 6.6; N, 10.2%). Loewenthal (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3962) reports 240° as the m.p. of the phenylpyrazolone derivative.

Ethyl β -2-Phenyl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylpropionate (IX).—The methiodide of β -dimethylaminopropiophenone (9 g.) in dry benzene (25 c.c.) was condensed with ethyl β -oxopimelate (13.6 g.) in presence of ethanolic potassium ethoxide, prepared from potassium (2 g.) and super-dry ethanol (40 c.c.) in the manner described before. When the initial reaction was complete, an additional amount of potassium ethoxide from potassium (1. g.) and ethanol (20 c.c.) was added and the whole refluxed for 4 hrs. The product was worked up in the usual way and the organic matter extracted thoroughly with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with saturated NaHCO_3 solution, but no acidic material was obtained. The ethereal solution was evaporated and the residue on distillation afforded the neutral ester (IX) (6.8 g., 50%), b.p. 170-72°/0.2 mm as a viscous oil. (Found : C, 75.3 ; H, 7.5. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 75.0 ; H, 7.3%).

It formed a *dinitrophenylhydrazone*, m.p. 141-42° (from benzene-methanol). (Found : N, 12.6. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$ requires N, 12.4%).

The corresponding *acid*, obtained by hydrolysis, could not be solidified, but it formed a crystalline semicarbazone, m.p. 238°. (Found : N, 13.7. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires N, 13.95%).

The *methyl ester*, prepared by heating the acid with MeOH-HCl solution, was obtained as a low-melting solid, m.p. 36° (from petroleum ether, b.p. 40-60°). (Found : C, 74.1 ; H, 7.1. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 74.4 ; H, 6.9%).

It formed a *dinitrophenylhydrazone*, m.p. 155° (from benzene-methanol). (Found : N, 12.8. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$ requires N, 12.8%).

Condensation of the Methiodide of 4-Diethylaminobutan-2-one with Methyl α -Methyl- β -oxoadipate—4-Dimethylaminobutan-2-one (7.5 g.), prepared according to Wilds and Shunk (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 469), was converted into its methiodide by addition of methyl iodide (3.8 c.c.), following the technique of Cornforth and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1855). To this was added a solution of methyl α -methyl- β -oxoadipate (10.5 g.) in dry benzene (50 c.c.), followed by an ethanolic solution of potassium (3.3. g.) in absolute ethanol (50 c.c.). The mixture was shaken at the room temperature for 2 hours and then refluxed on the water-bath for an additional period of 2 hrs. It was then cooled, decomposed with 2*N*- H_2SO_4 , and the benzene layer separated. The aqueous layer was once extracted with ether and the combined organic layer was repeatedly washed with NaHCO_3 solution. The total bicarbonate extract was then carefully acidified with HCl (conc.) and the precipitated organic matter was taken up in ether, dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated to leave a gummy residue (XVI or XVII) (9.1 g., 70%). This was esterified by an ethereal solution of diazomethane and the ester distilled in high *vacuo* to provide a colorless oil, b.p. 155-60°/0.2 mm. (Found : C, 61.4 ; H, 7.4. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 61.4 ; H, 7.1%).